

Stucco Art of Kyaung-Gyi-Nyi-Ama Temple at Bagan

Kyawt Hmu Aung*

Abstract

Kyaung-Gyi-Nyi-Ama, temple no. 997 at Bagan, was situated at South East of Thiripyitsaya, North East of Sitanagyi Stupa (stupa no. 987), Coordinates –N: 41.625, E: 6.630. It was medium size single storey temple, square central shrine and South, West and North foreparts. The temple entrance gate faces to the east. At the top there was two back rests, one of the back rest, on the arch pediment has a relief of pantheon or nat figure and it was amazing one. The figure of pantheon or nat can't found at other temples. It is one and only so that it was difficult to make comparative study with other temples. The whole exterior wall of this temple is decorated with full of beautiful figure and floral stucco art design. It is not exterior ordinary art. The artist created stucco works on their religious beliefs, their artistic feelings and emotions played important part in their creative process, they made art works on the exterior walls of temple. The temple may be constructed late 13th century temple or early 14th Century.

Introduction

Kyaung-Gyi-Nyi-Ama, temple no. 997, was situated at South East of Thiripyitsaya, North East of Sitanagyi Stupa (stupa no. 987), Coordinates –N: 41.625, E: 6.630 in a walled enclosure with gateway on East and West, together with monuments; 998 and 1000 to 1002. It was medium size single storey temple, and square central shrine and South, West and North four parts. The Temple had consisted of two plans, square central shrine has 5.66 _ 5.65 m, and entrance hall had 4.42 _ 4.65 m and on east side, with porch and lateral porches. Window was on South, West and North foreparts, and four upper parts, there were three terraces, first square terrace with corner stupas, the second square terrace with two projections, axial niches and corner stupas, the third square terrace had two projections with axial niches and square tower was top of the third square terrace. Upper part of square tower was destroyed. Temple no. 997, Kyaung-Gyi-Nyi-Ama temple (ama) is constructed with the use of brick masonry, average brick had 36 x 18.5 x 5 cm. Cloister vault was used over the shrine. Barrel vaults were used over the vestibule and porch Barrel vault hipped at east end over entrance hall, and low barrel vault was used over foreparts and porch. Flat arch was used over the windows and interior niches. It was also used the stone pavement and thresholds. There was one seated Buddha facing East against the screen wall of temple and it was destroyed. At the exterior of temple, stucco mouldings were found still in place: 25% such as ornate cornice and pediments, friezes with triangles, pilasters, urn-profiled base and tasseled frieze with pointed obovals, plasters with corner figures, base with recess, tower lancets with figure. Among them, this paper especially focused on stucco art of the temple. At present, beautiful stucco art were found at some part of Kyaung-Gyi-Nyi-Ama temple, such as dado, back rest, arch pediment, curls, base of the pillar, and corner pediment.

The temple entrance gate faces to the east, at the top there was two back rests, one of the back rest, on the arch pediment has a relief of pantheon or nat figure and it was amazing one, we can found pantheon or nat relief in this temple only, no other temples has pantheon or nat relief.¹ The pantheon or nat was sitting in squatting on the arch pediment on the apex of the first back rest, the head was like a beautiful lotus blossom, his hand was holding an object, the

¹ Fig. 1, two back rests of Kyaung-Gyi-Nyi-Ama (Ama), temple no. 997, Pichard, P. (1992). "Inventory of Monuments at Bagan", Volume (1-8), KISCADALE EFEO UNESCO, Paris, Field work

*Dr., Professor and Head, Department of Archaeology, Dagon University

wrist of the hand stucco was damaged already therefore we can't know what object he was holding but It was think that he hold a lotus bud in his hand.²

The figure of pantheon or nat can't found at other temples so that it was difficult to make comparative study with other temples, there was a snake head at the centre of the curl and at the right there were three snake heads guarding the entrance gate of the temple.³ Descending snake head rest on the shoulder of makara and guarding the entrance of temple, the same position series of snakes relief were formed, thus the entrance gate was guarded by 14 snakes, the snakes were water snakes.⁴ There were lotus blossom on the snakes, pantheon or nat was sitting on the lotus, this nat can be identify as Tantric Buddhist carved this stucco and according to the Brahmanism and Jainism the pantheon or nat was born from the pure water.

Both sides of the pantheon or nat relief there were arch pediments with bird figures and lotus florals, the pantheon or nat is sitting on the lotus and around the births, we can identify that the pantheon or nat is live on the water and the temple also arises from the water, thus the pantheon or nat is temple guardian pantheon or nat. At the right of the back rest, at the south side of the arch pediment there was figure of swans or hintha or duck biting eatable foods in the mouths and small pheasant was uplifting the heads, on the north side of the arch pediments there were figures on hen, snake heads and cranes—the creatures happily and merrily living in the water were formed at the centre of the frame with floral designs as a ornamented arch pediments.⁵

Mostly we can found birds and lions on the arch pediments, snake was formed in the arch pediments and it was rare stucco art works. At the corner pediments of the first back rest there were figures about the lion leap forward from the makara's mouth, the lion was afraid of makara and looks behind, three small fish leap out from the makara's mouth, one of the fish was reached directly to the snake's mouth all the relief were beautifully perforated by stucco art works.⁶ There was second back rest on the first back rest but the stucco art works on the second back rest was totally damaged therefore we missed a chance to study the stucco works. There were three curls from south side of the second back rest, on the second curl the snake's with two tongues were decorated by stucco floral design, the length of the snake crawl up to the first curl and fall down to the third curl, between the first and second back rest series of lotus can be found also.⁷

At the south side lateral porch of vestibule and on the upper part of two corner pediments there were running lions, on the arch pediments there were hintha birds on the snake, those figure were circling around the summit pediment. There was no art work or figure at the middle summit pediment.⁸ Two pillars backing the back rest a figure on small bird standing in looking back wards posture.⁹ In the triangular frame of the base of the pillar of the temple there was an ogre head as like three snake heads,¹⁰ floral designs like leafs, tasseled

² Fig. 2, first back rest and pantheon or nat; Fig. 3, pantheon or nat figure

³ Fig. 4, snake heads guarding the entrance gate of the temple

⁴ Fig. 2 and Fig. 4

⁵ Fig. 5. first backrest of temple no. 997; Fig.6, hintha, peathenon, lotus and two heads of snakes; Fig.7, arch pediments from south side of first backrest; Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, arch pediments from North side of first backrest

⁶ Fig. 10, lion, snake, fishs and Makara figure from corner pediment of first backrest at temple no. 997

⁷ Fig. 4, snake heads guarding the entrance gate of the temple

⁸ Fig. 11, south side lateral porch of vestibule; Fig. 12, running lions and hintha birds from backrest at south side lateral porch of vestibule, at temple no. 997

⁹ Fig. 15, small bird figure, pillar of south side lateral porch of vestibule, at temple no. 997; Fig. 11 south side lateral porch of vestibule

¹⁰ Fig. 13 an ogre head as like three snake heads, corner figure on plaster, at base of the pillar, south side lateral porch of vestibule, at temple no. 997

frieze with pointed obovals were put at the cornice of the temple. Between the pointed leaf shape floral there were two birds– male and female– facing each other and those figures were made in floral designs.¹¹ At the capital of the temple an ogre head figure was carved in the triangular frame, and at the corner bend of widow on the south side of central shrine stucco designs were wonderful– on the figure of the standing lion there was circular shape floral, the floral were big to small and perforated in detail.¹²

Results / Findings

Kyaung-Gyi-Nyi-Ama, temple no. 997, has the wonderful art works of stucco. The whole exterior wall of this temple is decorated with full of beautiful figure and floral stucco art design. The temple entrance gate faces to the east. At the top there was two back rests, one of the back rest, on the arch pediment has a relief of pantheon or nat figure and it was amazing one. The figure of pantheon or nat can't found at other temples. It is one and only. The pantheon or nat was sitting in squatting on the arch pediment on the apex of the first back rest of east side of this temple, the head was like a beautiful lotus blossom, the body has human form as like as man, his hand was holding an object, the wrist of the hand stucco was damaged. According to the form and style of the figure, the mail nat or pantheon was one of the Brahmanism or Jainism or Tantric Buddhist or Mahayana Buddhist pantheon or nat, he was born from the pure water and then guarding the entrance gate of the temple.

Discussion

It is not exterior ordinary art. The artist created stucco works on their religious beliefs, their artistic feelings and emotions played important part in their creative process, they made art works on the exterior and interior walls of temple. These stucco arts design are represent the belief, custom and their Buddhism concepts of the people of Bagan.

Conclusion

Most of the religious buildings in Bagan concerns with Buddhism. Stucco art works of Bagan period were mostly base on Buddhism, stucco artists conveys the essence of Buddhism with their creative imagination, thus those art works represent Buddhist philosophy and can be named as Buddhist art works of Bagan. . The whole exterior wall of this temple is decorated with full of beautiful figure and floral stucco art design. The artist created stucco art works on the exterior and interior walls of temple. Some of stucco art were found outer part of the of Kyaung Gyi Nyi Ama temple at Bagan , It may be constructed late13th century or early 14th Century.

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¹¹ Fig.14, tasseled Frieze with pointed leaf, at cornice of the temple no. 997; Fig. 16, two birds– male and female facing each other, in the tasseled frieze with pointed leaf

¹² Fig. 17, standing lion and floral design, widow on the south side of central shrine from temple no. 997

References

Field Work

Pierre Pichard, Inventory of Monuments at Pagan, (Volume 1-8), Volume 4, KISCADALE EFEO UNESCO, 1994

Fig. 1. Two back rests

Fig. 2. First backrest and Pantheon

Fig. 3. Pantheon or nat

Fig. 4. Snake heads guarding the entrance gate of the temple

Fig. 5. First backrest

Fig. 6. Hintha, peathenon, lotus and two heads of snakes

Fig. 7. Arch pediments from first backrest, from north side

Fig. 8. Arch pediments from first backrest, from south side, hintha and pheasant

Fig. 9. Arch pediments from first backrest, from north side, hen, snake heads and cranes

Fig. 10. Lion, snake, fishes and Makara figure from corner pediment of first backrest

Fig. 11. Lateral porch of vestibule, south face

Fig. 13. An ogre head as like three snake heads, corner figure on pilaster at base of the pillar, south side lateral porch of vestibule

Fig. 12. Backrest of lateral porch, south face, snake, lion and hintha

Fig. 14. Tasseled Frieze with pointed leaf at cornice

Fig. 15. Small bird figure, on pillar of south side lateral porch of vestibule

Fig. 16. Two birds- male and female, facing each other, in the tasseled frieze with pointed leaf.

Fig. 17. Standing lion and floral design, corner bend of widow, south side of central shrine,